

The role of conjunctions in English language teaching

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Abstract

Most Conjunction in English in English are short, but they hold a significant place in designing English sentences. Sometimes, we do not even notice this tiny conjunction in sentences but they are everywhere in English writings. Ignoring these conjunctions can lead to several English mistakes that make writing pieces full of errors. Conjunctions are the ‘joining words’ of a language. A sentence is broken up into parts and joined together as a whole by using these connecting words of the English language. Conjunctions help to make a sentence flow smoothly by joining phrases and clauses, showing the relationship between connected ideas.

There are three main types of conjunctions in the English language: coordinating, subordinating and correlative.

Key words: resembling, suitable, correlative, unimaginable, smooth, leading, relationship, joined, clauses.

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Большинство союзов в английском языке короткие, но они занимают важное место в построении английских предложений. Иногда мы даже не замечаем этого крошечного союза в предложениях, но в английских произведениях они есть повсюду. Игнорирование этих союзов может привести к нескольким ошибкам в английском языке, из-за которых написание текстов будет полно ошибок. Союзы – это «соединяющие слова» языка. Предложение разбивается на части и объединяется в единое целое с помощью этих соединительных слов английского языка. Союзы помогают сделать предложение

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плавным, соединяя фразы и предложения, показывая связь между связанными идеями.

В английском языке существует три основных типа союзов: сочинительные, подчинительные и соотносительные.

Ключевые слова: сходное, подходящее, соотносительное, невообразимое, плавное, ведущее, отношение, соединенное, придаточные.

Despite being tiny, no one can ignore the importance of conjunction in English. They are some of the most important words in English. They play a very crucial role in designing the sentences that we speak and write a daily basis.

A conjunction, like a noun, verb, or pronoun, is a part of speech. A conjunction's primary function is to join together other parts of speech.

Conjunctions can combine two basic words:

Do you like ice cream or chocolate?

I run and exercise every morning.

They are also used to combine different clauses. Such as:

Until next week, I cannot afford to buy a new mobile.

Additionally, you can use a conjunction to combine two sentences into one. For instance:

I can sing.

My best friend can dance.

You can use the conjunction “and,” and create one sentence. For instance:

I can sing and my best friend can dance.

Sometimes two sentences may look quite different from one another but once, they are connected with conjunction they make sense. Let us look at it with the help of an example:

I like my teacher.

I don't like the arts.

These two sentences are different from one another. But they can make sense with the help of the right conjunction. For example:

I like my teacher but I don't like the arts.

Now you know, how important as well as convenient Conjunctions in English are.

Conjunctions are very common. Once you've mastered the ability to construct basic sentences in English, the next logical step is to learn conjunctions. To learn their usage at an advanced level, you can get your hands into italki's lesson plans. It is a well-established language learning platform with around 7200+ online English tutors that will help you learn English online in a systematic way. The lessons will help you develop an understanding of English prepositions, vocabulary, conjunction, other parts of speech, etc.

Conjunctions are used to combine two or more objects, phrases or clauses. It can also be termed as connectors as they are employed in sentences to make connections. Conjunctions can normally be found in the latter part of a sentence if they are used to connect clauses. If conjunctions are used to connect objects or phrases, they can appear in the beginning, middle or end of the sentence according to the position of the objects or phrases.

Definition of a Conjunction

A conjunction, according to the Cambridge Dictionary, is defined as “a word such as ‘and’, ‘but’, ‘while’, or ‘although’ that connects words, phrases, and clauses in a sentence.” The Merriam Webster Dictionary defines a conjunction as “an uninflected linguistic form that joins together sentences, clauses, phrases, or words.”

A conjunction is “word that joins words, phrases or sentences, for example and, but or so”, according to the Oxford Learner’s Dictionary. The Collins Dictionary gives a slightly different definition. According to it, a conjunction is “any word or group of words, other than a relative pronoun, that connects words, phrases, or clauses.”

Types of Conjunctions

Conjunctions are mainly used to join actions, ideas and thoughts. They are categorised into three main types:

Coordinating conjunctions – used to combine two independent clauses. Examples of coordinating conjunctions are for, and, nor, but, or, yet and so.

Subordinating conjunctions – used to combine an independent clause and a dependent clause. Examples of subordinating conjunctions are if, although, though, after, before, because, as if, unless, until, when, while, etc.

Correlative conjunctions – used to combine two phrases or parts of the sentence which have equal importance within a sentence. Examples of correlative conjunctions are not only...but also, either...or, neither...nor, whether...or, rather...or, if...then, etc.

Examples of Conjunctions

Have a look at the following sentences to understand how conjunctions can be employed in sentences.

Sruthi and I visited Gokarna last weekend.

Do you have a rough notebook or at least a rough sheet of paper?

I did not go to work today because I was not keeping well.

She did not like the food, yet she ate it.

I will be leaving tomorrow so I am trying to finish all the pending assignments.

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List of Most Commonly Used Conjunctions in Daily Communication

Given below is a list of most commonly used conjunctions that you can use in your daily communication.

Examples of Conjunctions

And	Or	Nor
But	Yet	So
Because	Still	For
Not only...but also	As	When
While	As soon as	If
Unless	In case	In addition to
Whereas	Though	Although
Until	Before	After
Even if	Rather than	So that
Either...or	As if	Neither...or
Both...and	Whether...or	Or else

Check Your Understanding of Conjunctions

Fill in the blanks with the most appropriate conjunctions in the following sentences:

1. Deepak _____ Santhosh are best friends.
2. Make sure you work hard _____ you will not be able to score good marks.
3. _____ Anna does not cook much, she loves baking.

4. Let me know _____ you will be able to make it to the party.
 5. I have to go home now _____ I really wish I could stay for some more time.
 6. I am not well _____ I decided to take a day off from work.
 7. _____ you work out regularly, you will not see any results.
 8. He had no money, _____ he was prepared to help me
 9. I could not find the place _____ I lost the map.
 10. _____ I was walking on the street, I found a wounded dog.
- Find out if you have answered it all correctly.

1. Deepak and Santhosh are best friends.
2. Make sure you work hard or you will not be able to score good marks.
3. Although Anna does not cook much, she loves baking.
4. Let me know if you will be able to make it to the party.
5. I have to go home now but I really wish I could stay for some more time.
6. I am not well, so I decided to take a day off from work.
7. Unless you work out regularly, you will not see any results.
8. He had no money, yet he was prepared to help me.
9. I could not find the place since/because I lost the map.

10. While I was walking on the street, I found a wounded dog.

Frequently Asked Questions on Conjunctions in English

Q1

What is a conjunction?

A conjunction is used to combine two or more objects, phrases or clauses. It can also be termed as connectors as they are employed in sentences to make connections.

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